

STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT OF GEOLOGICAL SCIENCE

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Annotation. It should be said that the systematic approach is not a special "privilege" granted to geology over time, but a necessity that arose due to the uniqueness of the field. The multifacetedness of systems, as well as the multi-interpretation of the concept of "system" is explained by the ideas of modern philosophy that the laws of nature are multi-quality, multi-faceted and cannot be returned in the form of separate laws of physics, geology and biochemistry. Many systems arise, are followed, and disappear with the ideas that propagate that system; at the same time, some systems are "lifetime". It's roughly like the difference in longevity between a checkerboard game, a multiplication table, and a chess game on asphalt. In our above example, three advantages of the systematic approach are shown: the introduction of the rules of the game, the alignment of the controlled objects based on knowledge, and the symbolic presentation of the methods of discovery of the intellectual field in the still unexplained system. In today's era, simple (two-link) and multi-link, stable and self-developing, controlled and controlled systems, like a game of intelligence, create incomparable opportunities to study the world around us.

Main part. The most important advantage of systems is the continuous unfolding of systematic areas, that is, areas that we choose and are the product of our

perception. The existence and development processes of animate and inanimate nature take place in the same direction. Human evolution is expressed in its transformation from primitive forms to aquatic animals, adaptation to living on land, crawling reptiles, and finally organisms with different levels of development. The crystallization of granite reflects the evolution of the origin and development of the Earth. First of all, ultrabasic rocks (minerals that form primary rocks - olivines) appear, then they are replaced by basaltic minerals (pyroxenes), in subsequent evolutions, pyroxenes give way to diorite minerals (amphiboles, plagioclases) and only after the mentioned processes, ternary granite consisting of quartz, feldspars and mica crystallizes. In both geology and biology, the laws of divergence (separation and separation) and convergence (convergence) operate with equal force during evolution. The radiative spread of species across regions with different physical and geographical conditions leads to the emergence of new species, genera and families in biology.

The exogenous erosion of geological structures and the related differentiation of substances cause the formation of entire series of sedimentary rocks. The closeness (or similarity) between the existence and living conditions of the reptiles of the Mesozoic era and the mammals of the Cenozoic era is manifested in the external similarities of the species of creatures that lived in absolutely distant periods from each other. Two distinctly different processes – the accumulation of quartz, feldspars and mica in eroded sedimentary rocks and the change of the general evolution of magmatism towards the increase in the amount of silica - create conditions for the appearance of the granitic layer of the earth's crust.

If we look for the conditions of manifestation of similarities, not the difference between living and inanimate nature, we will witness the difference between these two worlds, which have not come close to each other since ancient times, as a result of the presence or complete absence of the axis of the fifth degree of symmetry.

possible A fifth axis of symmetry cannot exist in the world of crystals formed on the basis of a fixed order. Plato (Plato) theoretically created a drawing of shapes based on regular pentagons, but medieval mathematicians proved that it is impossible to

create a closed geometric shape in them. A six-sided snowflake can be shown as a symbol of inanimate nature. At the same time, it is appropriate to bring a five-pointed starfish as a symbol of living nature. There is a representative of the world, which acts as a kind of "border" between living and non-living nature, which is moving along the path of evolutionary development in mutual harmony, and we call it "virus". This condition (that is, the property of receptivity to both living and non-living nature) allows it to enter a living cell on the basis of the "Trojan horse" principle. In order to adapt its structure to new conditions and "survive", the virus takes a six-sided form: it kills the cell and sends it to the mineral world. Due to these and similar features, it (that is, the virus) is a real "boundary". The fifth-order arrow simplifies and accelerates biochemical reactions associated with potential differences by disrupting the structure formed on the basis of a fixed order in the crystal world. In addition, the interpretation of entropy as a measure of disorder and the conclusion that the Universe will end thermodynamically, as a result, contradicts both the results of biological evolution and the view that the geological structure of the Earth is complicated by rhythmically repeating tectonic processes.

Nevertheless, modern physical science, although evolution is irreversible, remains steadfast in its idea that rapid increases in entropy occur continuously, depending on the direction. Another point is that entropy may not be a measure of disorder, and thus of simplifications and decays [6]. As in ecology, it is necessary to know and use the laws of nature without fighting against them [4].

The formation of the theory of the evolution of the Earth is not a reality with a very long history. It follows from this that it is inevitable that a true integration of the sciences included in the complex of natural sciences will take place.

It is not unnatural that different social realities and processes occur within the landscape layer system. These realities and processes are guided by the laws of nature, just like geology, geography and biology. This fact is masked by the incorrect use of mathematical methods of processing materials related to the social sphere. [6]. Social variables are non-additive, meaning they cannot sum in an arithmetic sense. For

example, Gaussian distributions, successfully used in natural sciences, are practically unsuitable for the analysis of social phenomena. Mathematically convenient processing of the data set related to social realities is effective when all phenomena and realities in the scenic layer are subject to the same laws.

Systems are within us, systems are around us - this is a subjective reality related to the laws of thought that aim to study everything in order. However, subjective systems are clearly ongoing natural processes, and in general, they are oriented towards the surrounding world. Philosophy looks for signs of the fundamental laws of nature from the theory of systems. However, as long as the idea of a single view of existence is not formed, philosophy serves science and follows it. This process will continue until the Universe becomes transparent and its essence becomes completely clear to us. In general, geology, having all points (not points) of fundamentality, important practical importance, historicity, worldview, can and should be the basis of natural sciences and natural education at all levels. For now, geology has de facto status. However, we have the right to expect its de jure status in the near future.

Literature:

1. Беруни и Ибн Сина. Переписка. - Ташкент: Фан, 1973. - 36 с.
2. Бордовский Г.А. Подготовка специалиста в области образования (структура и содержание). - СПб., 1994. - С. 3-8.
3. Жиров А. И., Мосин В. Г., Соломин В. П. Создание, формирование и функционирование образовательных систем. - СПб., 1999. - 91с.
4. Нестеров Е.М. Геология в современном естествознании Сб. «Образы геопространства». - СПб.: Изд-во СПбГТУ, 2000. - С. 176-187.
5. Солнцев В.Н. Системная организация ландшафтов. Проблемы методологии и теории. - М.: Мысль, 1981. - 240 с.
6. Хайтун Д.С. Мои идеи. - М.: Агар, 1998. - 239с.